

IDEOLOGICAL STRUGGLE ON THE POLIGONS OF IDEOLOGY IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Nowadays, in the era of globalization, world politics is prone to continuous changes. Looking at the political landscape of the world, we can observe that various large and small political crises, economic crises and armed conflicts are increasing in it.

The international security system is faced with new non-traditional threats. In some cases, it is possible to observe that old problems appear in a new form. The unpleasant events happening in different regions of the world are deeply disturbing to any sane person, which requires serious thinking. Threats arising in different forms, confrontations due to national-religious and inter-confessional enmity, bloodshed due to disputes are causing serious concern to humanity. Indifference, thinking that such a reality is far from us, is harmful for the future of both society and nation.

Therefore, always being aware of events and happenings in the world - be it constructive or destructive - requires an approach with a sense of concern for the destiny and future of the country.

Unfortunately, it is not a secret to anyone that the events taking place on a global scale in the conditions of globalization cause not only fear in every person, but also "ideological panic" in the entire society. Therefore, "ideological panic" is the presentation of problems in order to frighten the population with the threat of compromising the existing state of peace in the society. Taking advantage of the happenings, drastic actions are taken to drag peoples, societies, states into war, to mislead them from their path. In the process of offering mutual relations, one side is favored and the other side is enmity. All kinds of fictions are developed and publicized about them that cause people to panic. In such a situation, it is out of the question that societies and states that do not have their own ideological views will fall into their trap [3].

Whether the appeals of such ulterior motives are covert or overt, it is important to remember that any indifference will cost us dearly. Falling into the trap of biased ideologies due to neglect is especially common in societies where there is an "ideological gap". Thankfully, the firm principle of not joining any military blocs adopted by our country and following only the path of peace and friendly relations encourages our country and people to be free from destructive ideologies that cause the danger of war.

In the conditions of globalization, the increasing ideological-ideological struggle in ideological landfills creates a favorable ground for the expansion of the minds and hearts of young people. In particular, the consequences of information attacks are manifested as the main and most profitable expansion in conquering the minds and hearts of the people of a particular region and country. In such a complex situation, it is a constant necessity to unite the society around the national idea, to mobilize it for constructive work in accordance with the requirements of the development strategy of establishing New Uzbekistan, and to increase awareness of the complex ideological processes taking place in the world [2].

In general, if we look at the world scene today, seeing how many people are suffering due to the wars and conflicts caused by various ideological threats, it shows that it is time to raise our heads from the problems of our daily routines and lifestyles. .

In ideological disputes, both the threat and the defender use methods of popularizing the idea. Therefore, science-based propaganda and propaganda will ultimately decide which side will win or lose. In this way, it can be said that the conflict of ideologies turns into a conflict of propaganda and propaganda.

In the 21st century, the process of receiving and processing information is not easy. Because the human brain suffers from the large amount of information and activates the self-defense system. According to G. Pochepsov, more information was produced in the last 30 years than in the previous five thousand years. An Englishman living in the 17th century was found to have received information only from the New York Times during his lifetime [4].

By the first quarter of the 21st century, several traditional and modern types of propaganda have appeared. Sociologist A. Suladze divides propaganda into positive and negative types depending on the effect of propaganda on emotions. We will focus on this approach because of its importance for our topic. Positive (constructive) promotion conveys one or another evidence to the consumer in a form that is useful for the recipient. The purpose of positive propaganda is to create social harmony, reconciliation, and educate people in the spirit of national and universal values. Positive propaganda performs educational, informative and explanatory tasks. Such propaganda takes into account the wishes of the recipients of information, there is no hidden goal (manipulation) and lies.

Negative (destructive) propaganda is an attempt to inculcate one or another idea or thought in people. The purpose of such propaganda is to arouse

social enmity, cause social conflicts, and intensify conflicts in society. This propaganda can be used to alienate people from each other. The goal is to create an illusion of reality, to inculcate false ideas and views into people for the benefit of the propagandist.

A national ideology built on a scientific and practical basis can overcome any threats in the process of ideological transformation. This can be done by strengthening the national and ideological immunity of our people, based on effective use of effective socio-pedagogical tools, and this is very important.

To sum up, the effectiveness of the reforms in the spiritual and educational sphere carried out in our country, so to speak, the spiritual and educational propaganda and campaigning works on the mind and consciousness of the future generation, historically rich will be inculcated by studying our spiritual heritage and, of course, by increasing the role of the Family Institute at the heart of such reforms. It is through these sciences that the ideology that expresses the good intentions and goals of the nation must have the power to mobilize everyone for the development of the country together for one goal and must be able to follow the people.

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